

In silico interactions of Methylxanthines with COVID-main protease: A Docking Study

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Abstract

COVID-19 might be a catastrophic global pandemic around the globe. Although most cases of infection are normal, in some instances there are respiratory problems with potentially serious lung injury. This virus may affect animals and humans, and its management is challenging since there is no appropriate vaccination or medications commercially available for COVID-19 treatments thus far. During this study, seven methyl xanthines were docked against COVID main protease. Pentoxiphylline demonstrated notable binding energy (-6.93 kcal/ mol). The study established pentoxiphylline to be potential lead molecule for further investigation and drug development process.

Keyword: *In silico*, Docking, Protease, Methyl Xanthenes, Binding Energy

1. Introduction

Coronaviruses are a family of viruses related to a variety of human and animal illnesses. These conditions vary from mild colds to more extreme ones. Coronavirus disease 2019 (COVID-19), also known as extreme acute respiratory syndrome coronavirus 2 (SARS-CoV-2), occurred in Wuhan City, China, at the end of December 2019¹. In present time, COVID-19 is a global threat for the populace, as the disease outbreak mindset is dangerously impacting a significant proportion of individuals and taking a massive number of lives on a regular basis. There are currently no specific therapeutic interventions available for COVID-19. The signs of COVID-19 are close to those of the general flu and can transform into pneumonia in few cases². The number of infections worldwide due to COVID-19 is also growing. The disease seems to be extremely contagious. Despite the plurality of COVID-19 cases, individuals undergo only minor sickness

and are able to cope up soon and retrieve without immediate treatment, people with severe underlying medical problems with life-threatening symptoms of pneumonia need hospitalization. However, at this moment in time, no suitable progress has been made in the treatment of COVID-19. Several efforts have been made to cure this condition, yet these medications are up-and-coming. As a consequence, there is a quickly developing emergency against this condition. Thus, it is crucial to develop possible agents for the treatment of the epidemic. Methylxanthines are a purine-derived class of drugs that are clinically used owing to their bronchodilatory and stimulating property³. This class contains many drugs, including the most commonly consumed caffeine in the world. Methylxanthines are approved by FDA for treatment of reversible airway restriction chronic bronchitis, and asthma. Apart from anti-asthmatic effect some of the methylxanthines are also recognized for their antiviral effects⁴. Among methylxanthines, Pentoxiphylline is well recognized for antioxidant and anti-inflammatory⁵ effects along with improvement in oxygen status in the patients⁶. The drug is reported to suppress tumor necrosis factor and other inflammatory cytokines⁵. It is also recognized for immunomodulatory and antiviral properties⁷. Clearly, it is very well recognised that the key protease (Mpro) of SARS-CoV-2 is among the most enticing antiviral drug targets, as viral protein maturation depends heavily on the activity of viral Mpro. Owing to these, the aim of present work was to study in silico interaction of methylxanthines with COVID-main protease.

2. The Hypothesis

Some of the methylxanthines are widely acknowledged for antiallergic and antiviral effects. So, we hypothesized that methylxanthines can be useful in inhibiting COVID/ SARS-CoV-2 by inhibiting the COVID-main protease.

Thus, the present research was aimed to investigate COVID-main protease inhibition by some methylxanthines by *in silico* techniques.

3. *In silico* studies

3.1 Software

Python 2.7- language was downloaded from www.python.com, Molecular graphics laboratory (MGL) tools and AutoDock 4.2 was downloaded from www.scripps.edu, Discovery Studio visualizer 4.1 was downloaded from www.accelerys.com.

3.2 Protein preparation

The three-dimensional crystalline structures of targeted proteins COVID-main protease (PDB ID : 6LU7) was retrieved from the Protein Data Bank (<http://www.rcsb.org/>). The coordinates of the structures were complexed with water molecules, and other atoms which are responsible for increased resolution and therefore the water molecules and het-atoms were removed using discovery studios and saved in .pdb format. The structures of test compounds Aminophylline, Caffeine, Dyxyphylline, Paraxanthine, Pentoxyphylline, Theobromine, Theophylline were obtained from Pubchem and stored in .pdb format.

3.3 Docking analysis

The docking analysis of reverse transcriptase was carried out using the Autodock tools (ADT) v1.5.4 and autodock v 4.2 programs. Aminophylline, Caffeine, Dyxyphylline, Paraxanthine, Pentoxyphylline, Theobromine, Theophylline were docked to all the target protein complexes with the molecule considered as a rigid body. The search was carried out with the Lamarckian Genetic Algorithm; populations of 100 individuals with a mutation rate of 0.02 have been evolved for ten generations. The remaining parameters were set as default. The docked structure was then visualized using Discovery Studio 2016 for obtaining the binding interactions.

4. Results

Molecular docking is a statistical approach that seeks to recognise the non-covalent bonding of proteins to small molecules. Docking determines the mode of interaction between the target protein and the small ligand for active site. Binding energy indicates the preference of the

particular ligand and intensity by which the compound associates and links to the pocket of the target protein. A compound with low binding affinity is favoured as a potential drug candidate. In order to assess the effect of active antiviral and methylxanthines on COVID-19, the seven methylxanthine were docked against against COVID-19 main protease.

In the present study, molecular structures of Aminophylline, Caffeine, Dyxyphylline, Paraxanthine, Pentoxyphylline, Theobromine, Theophylline were downloaded from PubChem and were converted to .pdb file for docking. The structure of COVID-main protease was obtained from protein databank. Genetic algorithm parameter was utilized to determine the best fit docking pose of the target and ligand. The binding energy and inhibition constant of docked complex was observed carefully along with study of hydrogen bond interaction (Table 1).

Aminophylline demonstrated the binding energy of -4.43 kcal/ mol and inhibition constant was 586.36 μm . Aminophylline demonstrated docking interaction with amino acids like Leu 141, Asn 142, Gly 143, Cys 145. This interaction was observed a ketone functional group located at purine. In case of Caffeine, there was a notable interaction at Gly 143, Ser 144, Cys 145. The ketone functional group demonstrated maximal interaction with the amino acids of protein. The binding energy for this interaction was the binding energy of -4.28 kcal/ mol and inhibition constant was 752.71 μm . The different type of interaction viz at Tyr 54, Met 49 was seen in case of Dyphylline. The binding energy was found to be binding energy of -4.66 kcal/ mol and inhibition constant was 387.01 μm . The interactions were observed at both of the hydroxyl group of the compound.

The docking interaction of COVID main protease with paraxanthine was observed at Leu 141, Asn 142, Gly 143. The interactions were observed at different locations. The nitrogen and carboxyl group present in purine participated in such interaction. Binding energy -4.37 kcal/mol and constant was 628.36 μm were observed. In case of Pentoxifylline, a noteworthy interaction was seen at Glu 166, Gln 192. The binding energy was -6.93 kcal/ mol and inhibition constant

was found to be 45.97 μm . A part from hydrogen bonding multiple van der Waals interactions were also observed in case of Pentoxiphylline (Figure 1). With theobromine, the interacting residues were Leu 141, Gly 143, Glu 166. The binding energy -4.41 kcal/mol was observed and inhibition constant was 588.24 μm . Theophylline demonstrated multiple hydrogen bonding at Leu 141, Gly 143, Ser 144, Cys 145 with binding energy -4.43 kcal/ mol and inhibition constant 570.16 μm .

5. Discussion

Coronavirus represents a group of viruses that can cause disease in humans and vertebrate animals. Thousands of people have been killed all over the world with a rise in the mortality rate each day. Infection hinders functions of the liver, central nervous system, cardiovascular and digestive process in animals and humans. There are currently no unique treatments available for COVID-19⁸. The signs of COVID-19 are close to those of the general flu and can develop into pneumonia in some cases⁹. Molecular docking is amongst the most common approaches in the field of computer-aided drug design for the discovery of small drug leads. With in modern period, computer-aided drug design is often used to easily encode and analyse large drug databases, minimizing a significant amount of resources, time and expense. Molecular docking is an important methodology that seeks to anticipate the primary 'binding modes' of the ligand mostly with 'protein' having known a 'three-dimensional structure.' The studies concentrated on binding modes that have been appropriate for substantial 'structural interaction' and offer valuable knowledge for the development of the inhibitors. Computational techniques for drug re-use strategies may be an effective way to work with \COVID-19 pandemic. In this study, methylxanthines were docked with COVID main protease, as protease had been shown to be a potent target of viral therapeutic targets for different viral pathogens. Drug repurposing together with molecular modeling was used for screening of potential COVID main protease inhibitor. COVID main protease¹⁰. It is a dimer of two equivalent subunits which together make the two

active sites. The protein folding is identical to serine proteases like trypsin, however cysteine amino acid and neighboring histidine have a protein-cutting response and an additional region stabilises the dimer¹¹. This arrangement has a peptide-like blocker attached to the binding site.

Numerous drugs have been investigated by computational techniques to study interaction of COVID protease. The molecular docking analysis revealed that methyl xanthines demonstrated excellent binding with COVID main protease. Pentoxifylline demonstrated excellent binding energy with COVID main protease. It could be a potential candidate for study biological studies on COVID main protease inhibition.

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Table 1: Docking interactions of aminophyllines with COVID main protease

Drug	Binding energy (kcal/mol)	Inhibition constant (μM)	Hydrogen binding residues
Aminophylline	-4.43	586.36	Leu 141, Asn 142, Gly 143, Cys 145,
Caffeine	-4.28	752.71	Gly 143, Ser 144, Cys 145
Dyphylline	-4.66	387.01	Tyr 54, Met 49
Paraxanthine	-4.37	628.36	Leu 141, Asn 142, Gly 143
Pentoxifylline	-6.93	45.97	Glu 166, Gln 192
Theobromine	-4.41	588.24	Leu 141, Gly 143, Glu 166
Theophylline	-4.43	570.16	Leu 141, Gly 143, Ser 144, Cys 145

Figure 1: Docking interactions of Pentoxyphylline with COVID main protease